

12- Month PhD Report December 2021

SUSTAIN

Responsible Partner: Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden (Supervisor: Olivier Rubin; Co-supervisor: Ann Lindberg)

Important Notes

- The full 9M report will be included in the Summary Progress Report due in September of each year.
- The full 12M report will be included in a new WP6 deliverable due in March of 2021/2022.
- A 'Summary' of each PhD project will be compiled from these 12M reports, and included in the Periodic report in February of each year.
 - The summary will be compiled from the content of the following sections :
 - Summary (approx. 500 words)
 - Overview of PhD progress
 - Deliverables and Milestones

1. Summary

Fieldwork:

From the 3rd to the 17th of October, I conducted fieldwork in Italy, interviewing experts from the veterinary institutes of different regions (in Brescia, Padova, Bologna and Teramo).

Research work:

The start of 2021 was used to finalise the manuscript “Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach”. I transcribed interviews that were conducted with public health and environmental experts from Italian institutes in autumn 2020. Additionally, I supported the NOVA project by analysing interviews. A survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March. Data gathering was completed in June 2021 and followed by analysis.

An edited book will be published by Oxford University Press and I was invited to write a chapter with Chris Degeling (University of Wollongong in Australia) on One Health and AMR in the European Union. This chapter is under construction. A author workshop was held in September. The chapter will be finalised in December. In March 2021, the “One Health governance” online survey was launched. From July 2021, data was analysed and based on the data, I am working on writing an article.

After the fieldwork in Italy, the process of transcribing interviews was initiated.

Scientific output:

Two articles were published in 2021:

- “Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach”. Medicina journal by MDPI.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>
- “One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination”. Scandinavian Journal of Public Health.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>

Teaching:

In spring 2021, I taught a Bachelor class on the topic of “Global governance Policy Area IV: Health” in the course “International Institutions and Global Governance”.

Conferences:

I participated at the

- OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 by engaging in the three minute competition and presenting my research at the conference (Lessons Learned from One Health Practices in Sweden and Italy). Additionally, I supported the organizing team in creating and presenting kahoot quizzes, which were held in the breaks of the conference, accessible for both the online and on-site participants.
- 14th European Public Health Conference via a poster presentation and a participation in a workshop called “The contribution of Environmental Impact Assessments to better health”
- GRASP festival, which was a conference (including some arts and performances), where I presented on-site some of my findings of the survey data.

2. Overview of the PhD project progress

The SUSTAIN PhD project is connected to WP7 of the OHEJP but it is not connected to specific tasks, deliverables or milestones.

Nevertheless, there has been progress. In 2021, data analysis was conducted as planned for the PhD project. This included transcribing interviews with experts from public health and environmental agencies and Italy. Data gathering for the interviews has been slowed down due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Due to travel restrictions, the remaining interviews were conducted in October 2021 with Italian veterinary experts. Subsequently, they were transcribed the analysis will start in 2022.

Data analysis was also conducted for the NOVA project “Surveillance barriers and opportunities as perceived by med-vet-food experts”.

Further, a survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March. The survey is addressed to ministries, EU institutions, international organisations and high level members of staff from public health, veterinary, environment and food agencies. The analysis of the survey data started after the end of the survey in July 2021 and an article is being prepared.

Within the PhD project, a number of articles must be produced. In March and June 2021, two articles were published (<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240> and <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>).

All teaching obligations (defined by Roskilde University) were completed after the spring semester 2020. However, I did teach a Bachelor class on the topic of “Global governance Policy Area IV: Health”.

3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

The SUSTAIN PhD project is connected to WP7 of the OHEJP but it is not connected to specific tasks, deliverables or milestones.

The start of 2021 was used to finalise the manuscript “Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach”, which is a co-authored article with Alberto Mantovani. The article was published in March 2021.

Another focus was put on transcribing interviews that were conducted with public and environmental experts in Italy at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità; the Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale; and the istituti zooprofilattici in October 2020 and 2021. The first round of transcriptions was concluded in April and the second round in December. The interviews will be analysed in 2022.

Additionally, I supported the NOVA project “Surveillance barriers and opportunities as perceived by med-vet-food experts”. After having conducted the interviews and started transcription and coding in 2020, we (Maria-Eleni Filippitzi & I) analysed the data in 2021.

A survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March. The survey was addressed to ministries, EU institutions, international organisations and high level members of staff from public health, veterinary, environment and food agencies. The online survey examined policy networks for One Health by understanding policy- and decision-making processes of One Health. The survey investigated political constrains for turning One Health topics into policy (science to policy) to shed light on opportunities for One health policy integration. Data gathering was completed in June July 2021 and followed by analysis. Based on this data, an article is being developed.

An edited book by Olivier Rubin, Erik Bækkeskov and Louise Munkholm (tentative title: Steering against Superbugs – The Global Governance of Antimicrobial Resistance) will be published by Oxford University Press and I was invited to write a chapter with Chris Degeling (University of Wollongong in Australia). The chapter will be about One Health and AMR in the European Union. This chapter is under construction and will be finalised by the end of this year. It will use a literature review as well as data from the survey (described above).

Within the PhD project, a minimum of three articles must be produced, of which at least two have to be self-authored. In 2020, two co-authored articles were published (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2020.100146> & <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-021-00277-y>). In 2021, one a co-authored and a self-authored article was published (<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240> & <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>). One singled-authored article is accepted and in the process of being published.

All teaching obligations (defined by Roskilde University) were completed after the spring semester 2020. However, I did teach a Bachelor class in April 2021 on the topic of “Global governance Policy Area IV: Health”.

Dissemination of the research was done by presenting at the OHEJP ASM 2021. At the conference in June, my PhD project was presented online at the 3MT competition. Additionally, the abstract I submitted was accepted for an oral presentation, where I had the opportunity to present my research titled "Lessons Learned from One Health Practices in Sweden and Italy" on-site at the ASM.

I also presented my research at the 14th European Public Health Conference with one poster and by participating in a workshop titled "The contribution of Environmental Impact Assessments to better health" where my focus was to discuss the benefits of the One Health approach within Environmental Impact Assessments. The event was online.

At the GRASP festival/conference, I presented some of my research based on the online survey titled "Challenges of policy actors to integrate the One Health approach into health emergency policy initiatives". The event was on-site in Roskilde, Denmark.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

Deliverables of Roskilde University's PhD School:

Every 6 months, the status of the PhD progress is assessed by the half-yearly evaluation, which entails detailed description of the past 6 months in terms of status, changes in the time schedule or budget plan, the nature of supervision, research stays at other institutes, the assessment of all attended events (courses, conferences) as well as teaching hours.

Teaching: 250 hours for the whole period of the PhD

- All teaching hours are completed

Total of 30 ects for whole period of PhD

From January to December 2021:

- Attendance and presentation at conference
 - o OHEJP ASM (Copenhagen, Denmark)
 - o European Public Health Conference (online)
 - o GRASP conference (Roskilde, Denmark)
- Courses
 - o 2 courses: Get your Article Published in a Social Science or Business Journal
 - o Work in Progress seminars (research group at Roskilde University)
 - o OHEJP Summer School
 - o Workshop on research communication
 - o Seminar on writing a Kappe (article-based dissertation)
 - o Quantitative research method workshop
- Minimum requirement of 30 ects is reached

Fieldwork and change of research environment stay, 3- 6 months

- All fieldwork and research stays are completed

Publications (Mandatory: three articles of which at least two are self-authored articles)

- Three co-authored articles published
- One single-authored article accepted and in the publishing process
- Remaining articles to be done in 2021 & 2022

Milestones

N/A

5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Teaching at bachelor level: International Institutions and Global Governance	Global governance Policy Area IV: Health	19.04.21	Roskilde University
OHEJP Summer School 2021	Environmental Issues in One Health: from risk assessment to surveillance	26.07.-06.08.21	Istituto Superiore di Sanità
Course: Get your Article Published in a Social Science or Business Journal (1/3)	Getting started (writing an abstract and an introduction)	18.05.21	Roskilde University
Virtual PhD Career Seminar	Understanding the job market, How do employers view PhDs as candidates for a position?, Competences and career paths as a PhD	12.04.21	Roskilde University
PhD Workshop on Research Communication	How to disseminate research to news outlets	09.09.21	Roskilde University
PhD Seminar on Writing a Kappe/Frame	Understanding the process of writing an article-based PhD dissertation	14.-15.09.21	Roskilde University
PhD Quantitative research method workshop	Sectional simple and multivariate regressions	16.09.21	Roskilde University
Course: Get your Article Published in a Social Science or Business Journal (2/3)	Writing a first draft of an article	26.10.21	Roskilde University

6. Publications and additional outputs

Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach

- <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>
- gold open access (no fees)
- Uploaded to Zenodo

Abstract for the OHEJP ASM 2021 - Lessons Learned from One Health Practices in Sweden and Italy

One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination

- <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>
- gold open access (no fees)
- Uploaded to Zenodo

Additional output

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7. Remarkable outcomes

Publication:

Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach

- <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57030240>

One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination

- <https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>

8. Impact & relevance

The PhD project has a unique angle on One Health. The project investigates One Health integration, implementation and how One Health is put into practice within public health, veterinary, food and environment institutes. The results of this research can be used by all partners to evaluate and consider their coordination and collaboration efforts. It can be used to enhance disease surveillance nationally and internationally. It produces useful knowledge and examples for institutes on challenges and opportunities for collaboration and for institutionalising One Health activities. On a political level, it will provide insight into sharing and translating knowledge between scientists and politicians.

9. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

The responses to previous ethical reviewers comments have been accepted and this is closed.

10. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on the project

Comments:

The Covid-19 pandemic has affected my PhD project, as there were changes in terms of fieldwork, conferences and courses. Conferences were postponed or rescheduled to online events, which impedes the ability to network.

My fieldwork was postponed or cancelled and cut short. In spring 2020, a research stay in Sweden at the Swedish Veterinary Agency was planned to conduct my fieldwork. However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, I remained in Denmark and conducted my interviews online via Microsoft Teams and Skype instead of conducting face-to-face interviews.

A three-month fieldwork stay in Italy at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità and the veterinary institutes in the autumn semester 2020 was shortened to a one month stay in October 2020 and another month stay in October 2021.

11. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information: /

12. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Roskilde University has a small "AMR Social Science" research group which I am part of. One project is the development of an edited book with the title "Steering against Superbugs – The Global Governance of

Antimicrobial Resistance”.

13. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP ASM – 3MT</i>		
Date:	<i>10.06.2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Online</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>YES</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>No</i>		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>550+</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP ASM – Oral Presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>10.06.2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Copenhagen, Denmark</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>No</i>		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>550+</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP ASM – Organising team for kahoot quizzes</i>		
Date:	<i>09.-11.06.2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Copenhagen, Denmark</i>		

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	Yes	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	No
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	<i>14th European Public Health Conference – Poster presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>10.-13.11.2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Online</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No

<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	14th European Public Health Conference – Workshop/Oral presentation		
Date:	12.11.2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	Yes

<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	Yes	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	GRASP – A FESTIVAL OF NEW IDEAS – Conference – Oral presentation		
Date:	18.11.2021		
Place:	Roskilde, Denmark		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	Yes
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No

<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>No</i>		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>30</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

